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Nitrate in Groundwater in Europe

Between 2010 and 2020 it decreased by 11.42%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the concentrations of nitrate-no₃ in the underground waters, measured in milligrams per liter (mg no₃/l). The data are taken from champions of wells and aggregated to average annual values. The nitrate can persist in groundwater for a long time and accumulate at high level through anthropogenic sources such as agriculture.

Ranking of countries by value of the presence of nitrate in groundwater in 2020. Malta is in the first place for the value of the presence of nitrate in the underground waters in 2020 with a value equal to 59.43, followed by Bulgaria with an amount of 30.51 Unit and from Belgium with 28.65 units. In the middle of the standings there are the Czech Republic with an amount of 18.71 units, followed by Slovakia with an amount of 18.62 units and by Switzerland with an amount of 14.65 units. They close the Cyprus ranking with an amount of 7.84, followed by Estonia with an amount of 5.5 units and Latvia with an amount of 3.93 units.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage variation of the presence of nitrate in the groundwater between 2010 and 2020. Serbia is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the presence of nitrate in the underground waters between 2010 and 2020 with an equal amount 391.95% equal to an amount of 9.25 units, from Latvia with an amount of 57.83% equal to an amount of 1.44 units, followed by Estonia with an amount of 54.93% equal to a amount of 1.95 units. In the middle of the standings there are the Czech Republic with an amount of -4.69% equal to an amount of -0.92 units, followed by Portugal with a value of -4.74% equal to an amount of -1.09 units and from Belgium with a value of -5.1% equal to an amount of -1.54 units. France close the ranking with an amount of -21.84% equal to an amount of -5.36 units, followed by Slovakia with an amount of -22.38% equal to an amount of -5.37 units and from Cyprus With a value of -83.45% equal to an amount of -39.54 units. Overall between 2010 and 2020 the value of the percentage variation of the presence of nitrate in the underground waters passed from an amount of 22.09 units up to a value of 19.5 units equal to a variation of -11.42% equal to a amount of -2.52 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. A cluster analysis with the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient is applied below. Specifically, three Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Estonia, Latvia, Serbia, Ireland, Slovenia, Switzerland;
- Cluster 2: Germany, Austria, France, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Portugal, Slovakia;
- Cluster 3: Cyprus, Malta.

From the point of view of clusterization it is possible to verify the presence of the following system of the Clusters or: C₃ = 33,635 > C₂ = 21,525 > C₁ = 12,03.

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Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is created below using the Euclidean distance. There are two network structures of which one is complex, and one is simplified. The complex network structure is indicated below or:

- Ireland has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.23 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Ireland for an amount of 0.23 units and with Switzerland for an amount of 0.2 units;
- Switzerland has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.2 units.

In addition, there is the following structure with simplified network or:

- Latvia and Estonia have a connection for a value of 0.2 units.

Conclusions. The nitrate present in the underground waters decreased by 11% between 2010 and 2020 on average for the countries considered. However, there has been a significant growth of nitrate in groundwater in some countries or Serbia with +391.95%, Latvia with +57.83% and Estonia with a value of +54.93%. The analyzed dataset presents various Missing Values. For example, data relating to Italy, Spain, Austria are missing. It is therefore difficult to grasp the real aggregate trend of the variable in European countries.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

